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Great Power Competition in the Bay of Bengal: Significance and Trends

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About the Contributor

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The locus of the Bay of Bengal (BoB) has been a grave hub of great power competition for years because of its geostrategic and geo-economic utility and magnitude. By the time the significance of the hub has not dwindled, rather been diversified and ubiquitous to the world stage that allured the great powers. In this respect, the United States, China and India are salient who take the BoB into account of their foreign policy and strategy with a distinct importance. Study shows that the recent emergence of the BoB is shedding light on a different trend shifted from co-operation to conflict based on the geo-economic and geopolitical dynamics. The traits that played a robust role behind the diverse trend in the Bay of Bengal encompasses a wide array of aspects such as the rise of India as a major power in the South Asian region from trade and economic perspectives, the phenomenal economic upswing and growth of China, and the geostrategic importance of the Bay of Bengal as a part of Indo-Pacific Strategy of the USA. These quintessential themes have recalibrated the crucial significance of the Bay of Bengal. Therefore, in his book, "Monsoon: The Indian Ocean and the Future of American Power", Robert D. Kaplan has signified the magnitude and likelihood of the 'Indian Ocean Region' as a next theatre of war and conflict. However, while the US' interest in the region is more about military and strategic confrontation with China, China's interest, to a broader extent, marks an economic persuasion. Along with them, India's economic and political performance as a major power in the BoB region is also irrefutable.

Great Powers in the Bay of Bengal

Great-power politics is not a new dimension in the world politics. There are many instances such as Afghanistan, Middle East, Cuba, Iraq and so on wherein great powers such as the United States,

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Soviet Russia and China have played crucial politics. From that delineation the BoB also is not new hub for great power rivalry though the dimensions and trends have shifted. Regarding the BoB hub, the United States, China and India are core powers to be taken into account. While the United States, according to contemporary status, and China are gauged as great-powers, India is considered as a major power with a potential of becoming great power. Despite having no geographical lineage to the Indian Ocean and the Bay of Bengal, the United States formulated its Indo-Pacific Strategy for geopolitical linkage and interest. The recent dynamics of establishing AUKUS, IPEF and recalibrating the QUAD and 'Blue Dot Network' with a view to thwarting the Chinese dominance, in the Indo-Pacific region along with the BoB have marked that the US is desperate to ensure its own geostrategic interest.

China may have a brawny industry and world market but the thing that is extremely needed to run the market is all about fossil-fuels such as oil, coal and gas. China takes advantage of the BoB route for their oil import which led them to be keen on having palatable relationships with coastal countries. To secure interest in the South China Sea and to reduce reliance on the Malacca strait, regarded 'Malacca Dilemma', through which China imports more than 80% of its oil, this Eastern great power is prospecting to have its oil transported through the sea route and roads of the BoB. As a major power and regional dominant power, India has always been at the center of the strategy regarding the Bay of Bengal. The BoB is quintessential for Indian economic prosperity. Per a 2013 report, 75% of oil and 95% of foreign trade have been imported through the SLOCs of the Bay of Bengal route. Not only for securing economic interests, but India has also taken major strategies to keep its predominance over the regional dynamics of geopolitics. By shifting from "Look East Policy" to "Act East Policy", India has let others know what foreign policy this South Asian giant pursues toward its eastern counterparts.

Why the Bay of Bengal is Significant to the Great Powers?

Not only for economic and political aspects but also for energy supply, marine transit and maritime dimensions, the Bay of Bengal has highly been marked and preferred in this region for the last few decades. Particularly, energy is an inexorable part and parcel for running industry and market. For these reasons the Bay of Bengal is regarded as a significant hub to the great powers.

Economic Perspective

With a view to exerting and implementing the BRI, however, China has been employing the BoB as an exigent part of SLOC. The BoB has been one of the core trade routes for the Chinese economy since Xi Jin Ping introduced the BRI project. Likewise, the US President Joe Biden's new IPEF has included the BoB as a very significant part for this economic framework. Besides, the BoB is remarkably crucial for the US' Blue Dot Economy and Indo-Pacific Corridor. On the other hand, India has established ITCOcean (International Training Centre for Operational Oceanography for extracting the resources and the blue economy of the bay. Due to this growing economic magnitude of blue economy, the littoral countries, emphasizing economic cooperation, have come up with the notion and establishment of BIMSTEC which added superfluous impetus in rising of behoof of this economic hub.

Political Dimension and Maritime Labyrinth

Looking at the political dimension, apart from Myanmar's subsequent military regime, the other countries of the Bay of Bengal exert a common political structure of democracy that led them to be keener on a collaborative approach regarding this bay. Bangladesh and India, particularly, exhibit a common and collective interest in having a stable bay of Bengal which would be used for not only economic purposes but also for political consensus. Maritime boundary dispute, in this regard, was an extreme hindrance. In order to have a solution to the maritime boundary dispute, Bangladesh raised the case in ITLOS and PCA in 2014 where the international authorities gave a verdict and urged to resolve the disputes.

While India is in maritime labyrinth with Bangladesh, in one side, it is in serious conflict with China in the South China Sea, on the other. As a result of such a maritime boundary labyrinth, the great powers get room for exerting power in such hub. For instance, China is deemed to have the most influence in the region which has been palpable since China and Bangladesh reached a deal about submarines. China, for ensuring its maritime interest in the BoB, has provided Bangladesh with two Ming-Class Type submarines which incident made India, according to Indian thinkers, vulnerable to a security aspect. As a counteraction, India also provided Myanmar with a submarine with a view to putting down china's hubris and obstructing the increase of Bangladesh's dominance over the region.

Energy Perspective

Energy is the basement and lifeline to run industry and market in this contemporary neo-liberal economic system. The development projects of the coastal countries have given rise to an inexorable need for energy. China and India, therefore, are highly dependent on the Bay of Bengal routes for importing the biggest part of the oil and fossil fuels from the Middle East through which China imports 75 percent while India does 95 percent. Moreover, China imports gas from Myanmar through the route. The US, Japan and Australia have also started considering the Bay of Bengal as an alternative energy supply route.

Marine Transit

As a marine transit, however, the Bay of Bengal is an elastic and indispensable location for the coastal countries. Saliiently, the Andaman and Nicobar Island near Malacca Strait provides crucial facilities for ship repair, free port, military logistical support and economic services. Belonging to the Bay of Bengal, some ports such as Mongla, Chittagong, Chennai, Kolkata, Yangon, Haldai and Tuticorin are crucially used as marine transit. Therefore, the Bay of Bengal has become the crucial marine transit for the great powers which spurred the significant rise of the region.

Recent Trends

Since the arrival of the Vasco Da Gama in the 15th century, the Bay of Bengal has long been used as a center of trade and commerce in the South Asia and all over the world. The core of the significance of this region was highly surrounded by economic aspects based on cooperation and collective efforts, which, to some extent, is still palpable in light of the BIMSTEC. By contrast, by the time, the geopolitical and geostrategic aspects have come to forth presenting the Bay of Bengal as a geopolitical hub for great power rivalry. In this regard, Robert D. Kaplan and many other scholars argue, 'the Bay of Bengal is going to be the next theatre of conflict and war.

From aforementioned data and evidences, it is beyond doubt that the United States has a grave concern in this region since China's emergence marks a very fast rise. In light of the 'Thucydides Trap' it is inevitable that the US and China will get into collision in the BoB in near future with view to establishing their geopolitical dominance. On the other hand, India's ambition to enter into great power groups will make the things more complicated as its interest will likely divert to serious politics from economic and cooperative aspects. Therefore, the BoB region is shifted

toward a hub of political conflict from economic cooperation and collectiveness. This conflict, as a result, will hamper the peace and stability of not only the small states like Bangladesh, Myanmar and Sri Lanka but also the whole region. The states should pursue more comprehensive, mutual and cooperative foreign policies so that the Bay of Bengal region can get rid of any catastrophic conflict or war.

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